

Molecular organization and effective energy transfer in iridium metallosurfactant–porphyrin assemblies embedded in Langmuir–Schaefer films

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Mixed Langmuir monolayers and Langmuir–Schaefer (LS) films containing the cationic metallosurfactant bis(2-phenylpyridine)(4,40-diheptadecyl-2,20-bipyridine)-iridium(III) chloride (Ir-complex) and the anionic tetrakis(4-sulfonatophenyl)porphyrin (TSPP) in 4 : 1 molar ratio have been successfully prepared by the co-spreading method at the air–water interface. The presence of both luminescent species at the interface, as well as the organization of the TSPP underneath the Ir-complex matrix in Langmuir and LS films, is inferred by surface techniques such as p–A isotherms, reflection spectroscopy, Brewster angle microscopy (BAM) and UV–visible absorption spectroscopy. A red-shift in the absorption band of the porphyrin under the compression of the mixed monolayer suggests the J-aggregation of the TSPP under the Ir-complex matrix. To date, this is the first report of Langmuir and/or LS films containing these two types of species together. Furthermore, the intermolecular energy transfer between Ir-complex and TSPP molecules in solution and in transferred mixed films is investigated through steady-state fluorescence and lifetime measurements. These results indicate that effective intermolecular energy transfer occurs from the Ir-complex to the TSPP molecules in LS films. The influence of the spatial proximity of donor and acceptor molecules has been studied by the insertion of lipid interlayers among them.

Introduction

Several methods to build well-ordered molecular assemblies are being developed as a current objective of the Supramolecular Chemistry.[1,2] For these purposes, the air–water interface is an ideal model, as it allows for the assembly of organized ultrathin films containing different molecules with various functions and well-defined architectures (composition, structure, and thickness), by using the Langmuir trough technique. Furthermore, Langmuir monolayers can be transferred onto solid substrates by vertical deposition (Langmuir–Blodgett film, LB) or horizontal touching (Langmuir–Schaefer film, LS). Among the different available deposition methods, these techniques offer the possibility of arranging molecules and preparing highly-ordered ultrathin multilayers with precisely controlled thickness at the molecular level. Therefore, LB and LS techniques are interesting not only in a fundamental way, but they are also powerful tools for studying distance dependent energy and electron transfer processes.[3] In this work, we report on the formation of a mixed monolayer at the air–water interface and transferred by the LS method onto a solid substrate, containing two luminescent molecules: an amphiphilic monocationic Ir(III) metallosurfactant, Ir-complex, and a tetraanionic water-soluble porphyrin, TSPP (see Scheme 1). The Ir-complex used here belongs to the family of organometallic triplet emitters, which are receiving great attention not only because of their

use in electroluminescent devices,[4–7] and gas sensing,[8–10] but also in biomedical applications.[11,12] Water-soluble porphyrins may be regarded as models of native porphyrin derivatives in the physiological state, as their structural simplicity, in comparison to the native analogues, facilitates the understanding of structure–biological activity relations. Moreover, porphyrin aggregates have attracted much attention as potential candidates for applications in non linear optics, nanometre-sized photoconductors, light-harvesting systems or optical sensors.[13–17]

Scheme 1. Molecular structures of amphiphilic iridium complex (Ir-complex), tetrakis(4-sulfonatophenyl)porphyrin (TSPP), dioctadecyldimethylammonium bromide (DOMA) and stearic acid (SA).

The literature concerning organized molecular films of cyclometalated iridium-(III) complexes is limited, and has been focused on the preparation of pure films of amphiphilic Ir(III) derivatives,[10,18] or mixed films containing water-insoluble complexes organized underneath a lipid matrix.[19,20] Valli et al. achieved densely packed LS films of an amphiphilic Ru(II) complex,[21] and more recently two reports have shown the deposition of LB films of amphiphilic iridium(III) complexes, mixed with polyoxometalates and alternated with an amphiphilic ruthenium complex for OLEDs application.[22,23]

To date the preparation of organized thin films of porphyrin derivatives has been studied by several research groups and a large number of works concerning water-soluble porphyrins have been published.[24–32] Among these works, the research carried out by Valli's group is of special interest,[31,32] who obtained bichromophoric LS films containing water-soluble porphyrins with other cationic surfactants. However, the fabrication of an iridium metallosurfactant–porphyrin film is reported, for the first time to our knowledge, in this work. In this way, the Langmuir technique has allowed us to assemble these two luminescent species together, which may behave as energy donor and acceptor units in an energy transfer process. Moreover, the influence of the spatial proximity of the Ir-complex and the porphyrin ring has been studied by the insertion of interlayers among them, allowing a control of the two emissions.

Experimental

Materials

The iridium metallosurfactant bis(2-phenylpyridine)(4,40-diheptadecyl-2,20-bipyridine)-iridium(III) chloride (Ir-complex) was synthesized following the procedure published elsewhere.[33] Tetrakis(4-sulfonatophenyl)porphyrin (TSPP), dioctadecyldimethylammonium bromide (DOMA), and stearic acid (SA) were purchased from Fluka, Sigma and Aldrich, respectively, and used without purification. Their molecular structures are depicted in Scheme 1. Pure organic solvents were obtained without purification from Aldrich (Germany). A mixture of chloroform/methanol, ratio 3 : 1 (v/v), was used as a spreading solvent for the Ir-complex. A mixture of dichloromethane, methanol and water, ratio 15 : 9 : 2 (v/v/v), was used as a spreading solvent for solving DOMA and TSPP. Ultrapure water, produced by a Millipore Milli-Q unit, pre-treated by a Millipore reverse osmosis system (>18.2MO cm), was used as a subphase. The subphase temperature was 21 °C with pH 5.7.

Methods

Two different models of Nima troughs (Nima Technology, Coventry, England) were used in this work, both provided with a Wilhelmy type dynamometric system using a strip of filter paper: a NIMA 611D with one moving barrier for the measurement of the reflection spectra, and a NIMA 601, equipped with two symmetrical barriers to record BAM images.

UV–visible reflection spectra at normal incidence as the difference in reflectivity (ΔR) of the dye film-covered water surface and the bare surface³⁴ were obtained with a Nanofilm Surface Analysis Spectrometer (Ref SPEC2, supplied by Accurion GmbH, Göttingen, Germany). The reflection spectra were normalized to the same surface density of Ir-complex by multiplying ΔR by the surface area, i.e., $\Delta R_{\text{norm}} = \Delta R A$, where A ($\text{nm}^2/\text{Ir-complex molecule}$) is taken from the surface pressure–area (p – A) isotherms. Images of the film morphology were obtained by Brewster angle microscopy (BAM) with a I-Elli2000 (Accurion GmbH) using a Nd:YAG diode laser with a wavelength of 532 nm and 50 mW, which can be recorded with a lateral resolution of 2 μm . The image processing procedure included a geometrical correction of the image, as well as a filtering operation to reduce interference fringes and noise. The microscope and the film balance were located on a table with vibration isolation (antivibration system MOD-2 S, Accurion GmbH) in a large class 100 clean room. The monolayers were transferred onto quartz substrates, cleaned in successive steps with an alkaline detergent, isopropanol, and ethanol and then rinsed with ultrapure water. The monolayers were transferred at a constant surface pressure by the Langmuir–Schaefer technique, i.e., by horizontal touching of the substrate and the interface covered with the mixed film. The multilayers were assembled by sequential monolayer transfer. The ratio of the transfer process to the solid substrates, t , was close to unity in all cases. UV–visible electronic absorption spectra of the LS films were recorded locating the support directly in the light path on a Cary 100 Bio UV–visible spectrophotometer.

The steady state fluorescence and excitation spectra were measured using a FS920 Steady State Fluorimeter (Edinburgh Instrument, Livingston, UK). The emission lifetimes were measured by a FL920 Fluorescence Lifetime Spectrometer (Edinburgh Instrument), based on the TCSPC (Time-Correlated Single Photon Counting) technique^[35] and using different picosecond pulsed diode lasers (372 and 406 nm). The luminescence decay curve analysis was performed by a deconvolution technique, where the experimental data were compared with a model decay function. The decay parameters were determined by a least-squares fitting routine, the goodness of the fit was assessed by the reduced χ^2 values obtained (range 1–1.2). All measurements were carried out at room temperature and solutions in the air-equilibrated solvent (dichloromethane/ methanol/water, ratio 15 : 9 : 2 v/v/v), using a 1.0 cm path length quartz cuvette.

Results and discussion

1 Surface pressure–area isotherms

The studied Ir-complex is amphiphilic and forms Langmuir monolayers on pure water. As this metallosurfactant is positively charged, mixed monolayers of Ir-complex and the anionic water-soluble porphyrin TSPP, in molar ratio 4 : 1, have been prepared by the co-spreading method[36] at the air–water interface. This mixing ratio corresponds to the stoichiometry to form neutral monolayers and thus we expect that all the porphyrin molecules remain bound to the complex matrix by electrostatic interactions, which was tested further on. The surface pressure–area (π -A) isotherms of the pure Ir-complex and the mixture Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) are shown in Fig. 1, and are expressed per Ir-complex molecule. In both cases, the collapse occurred around 40 mN m⁻¹.

Fig. 1 Surface pressure_area (π -A) isotherms of the Ir-complex monolayer and the Ir-complex : TSPP mixed monolayer in a molar ratio 4 : 1 (T = 21 °C).

In previous work,[28,37] a mixed monolayer containing TSPP and the lipid dioctadecyldimethylammonium bromide (DOMA) in a 1 : 4 molar ratio was studied at the air–water interface. In such a system, the isotherm of the mixed film was expanded compared to that of the pure lipid isotherm. Any expansion with respect to the pure lipid isotherm is clear evidence of the presence of the porphyrin molecules at the interface. In fact, this effect is normally observed in mixed films composed by a lipid matrix. However, the opposite phenomenon was observed for the Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) mixed film, as the isotherm was shifted to smaller effective molecular areas compared with the pure complex, for all surface pressure. Then, the presence of the TSPP dye at the interface, together with the Ir-complex molecules, will be demonstrated by reflection spectroscopy.

The morphology of the Ir-complex and mixed Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) films was directly visualized by BAM, simultaneously to the π -A isotherm register. In the case of the pure Ir-complex, small bright domains appeared from 5 mN m⁻¹, increasing in number and covering the whole surface at high surface pressure (images not shown). However, for the mixed film, a homogeneous monolayer was observed during the compression process, and the reflectivity of the interface increased gradually as the monolayer was compressed (images not shown). This fact may indicate that the TSPP molecules are homogeneously distributed over the whole surface underneath the Ir-complex matrix. Then, the use of porphyrin molecules as counterions in the mixed film helps to homogenise and distribute the Ir-complex molecules along the air–water interface.

2 Reflection measurements

Reflection spectroscopy allows the direct detection of the presence of chromophore molecules located at the air–water interface,³⁴ and gives us valuable information on their organization, density, and orientation. In Fig. 2, a series of reflection spectra at different surface pressures (π) recorded during the compression of the Ir-complex monolayer are shown (solid lines).

Fig. 2 Reflection spectra DR of the Ir-complex monolayer, from $\pi = 0 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$ to 39 mN m^{-1} . Inset: normalized reflection spectra of the Ir-complex monolayer, $\Delta R_{\text{norm}} = \Delta R \times A_{\text{Ir-complex}}$.

For comparison, the spectrum of Ir-complex in chloroform/methanol (3 : 1 v/v) solution is also included (dashed line). The bands between 240 and 320 nm can be assigned to ligand-centered $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions involving the phenylpyridines at higher energy and the bipyridines at lower energy.[38] As can be observed, ΔR increased with the applied surface pressure, indicating that the surface concentration of the Ir-complex increased under compression of the film. Furthermore, it should be mentioned that reflection spectra were measured during several compression and expansion cycles (data not shown), being these spectra identical during these processes and during several cycles. Inset in Fig. 2 shows the normalized reflection spectra of the Ir-complex film, ΔR_{norm} , being $\Delta R_{\text{norm}} = \Delta R \times A_{\text{Ir-complex}}$, where $A_{\text{Ir-complex}}$ (nm^2 per molecule) is taken from the isotherm. As can be observed, the normalized spectra did not experience any significant change in terms of intensity, shape and position of the bands as a function of the surface pressure. This result indicated the absence of changes of orientation and association of the metallosurfactant during the compression of the film. The Ir-complex molecules present at the air–water interface can be quantified. For low values of absorption (e.g., 0.01), the reflection ΔR is given in a reasonable approximation by [24,34,39,40]

$$\Delta R = 2.303 \times 10^3 G f_{\text{orient}} \varepsilon \sqrt{R_s} \quad (1)$$

where $R_s = 0.0241$ is the reflectivity of the air_water interface at normal incidence, ε is the extinction coefficient given as $\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, f_{orient} is a numerical factor that takes into account the different average orientation of the chromophore in solution as compared to the monolayer at the air_water interface and G is the surface concentration in mol cm^{-2} . Additionally, surface concentration can be expressed as $G = 10^{14}/N_A A$, being N_A the Avogadro number and A the area per molecule in nm^2 . Then, the normalized reflection can be expressed as:

$$\Delta R_{\text{norm}} \times 100 = 5.4 \times 10^{-6} f_{\text{orient}} \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

For the Ir-complex, ΔR_{norm} can be calculated from eqn (2). The orientation factor can be considered equal to unity for the Ir-complex,[42] and assuming $\epsilon = \epsilon_{\text{solution}}$ at λ_{max} ($\epsilon_{\text{sol},260} = 8 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), we obtained $\Delta R_{\text{norm}} \times 100 \approx 0.43 \text{ nm}^2$. This value is in very good agreement with those obtained at any surface pressure (see inset in Fig. 2). This fact indicated that all the Ir-complex molecules initially spread remain at the air–water interface.

Fig. 3 shows the reflection spectra (a) and the normalized reflection spectra (b), obtained at different surface pressures for the Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) monolayer. Together with the absorption bands due to the Ir-complex, all spectra showed the intense Soret band typical of porphyrins at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 422 \text{ nm}$, which was clear evidence of the presence of TSPP molecules in the mixed monolayer. The wavelength of the peak at 422 nm corresponds to the position of the Soret band in solution, and therefore this peak must be related with non-aggregated porphyrin. As the film was compressed, the reflection intensity of both chromophores increased, which indicated that their surface densities in the monolayer also increased. Reflection spectra have also been measured during several cycles (data not shown) and identical spectra have been obtained, i.e., there was no loss of TSPP molecules toward the subphase.

Fig. 3 (a) Reflection spectra ΔR of the Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) monolayer, from $\pi=0\text{mNm}^{-1}$ to 35 mN m^{-1} . Inset: wavelength of maximum absorption of TSPP versus area per TSPP molecule; (b) normalized reflection spectra of the mixed monolayer, $\Delta R_{\text{norm}} = \Delta R \times A_{\text{Ir-complex}}$.

At low surface pressure, TSPP molecules can be quantified by eqn (2). In this case, $\epsilon_{\text{sol},420} = 4.5 \times 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. At this pressure, TSPP molecules are supposed to be flat oriented, which means $f_{\text{orient}} = 1.5$ (see further comments). Then, the reflection was calculated to be $\Delta R_{\text{norm}} \times 100 \approx 0.91 \text{ nm}^2$. This value agreed well with that measured at 0 mN m^{-1} ($\Delta R_{\text{norm}} \times$

100 \approx 0.88 nm², see Fig. 3). Therefore, the former assumption of flat orientation and no loss of porphyrin TSPP molecules toward the aqueous subphase is correct.

Differently from the Ir-complex reflection bands, the porphyrin Soret band shifted to longer wavelengths upon compression. Inset in Fig. 3a plots the maximum absorption wavelength against the area per TSPP molecule. In previous work,²⁸ a blue-shift by \sim 12 nm with respect to the maximum wavelength at low surface pressure was observed for the DOMA : TSPP (4 : 1) system. In this case,²⁸ the wavelength shift was due to the appearance of a new band, related to the formation of TSPP dimers, i.e., only two maxima were detected along the compression.²⁸ However, for the Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) mixed monolayer, the maximum wavelength red-shifted continuously from $\lambda_{\max} = 422$ nm until it reached a constant value $\lambda_{\max} = 427$ nm, as shown in Fig. 3a (inset).

The reflection spectra have been normalized by the area per Ir-complex molecule (Fig. 3b), $\Delta R_{\text{norm}} = \Delta R \times A_{\text{Ir-complex}}$, where $A_{\text{Ir-complex}}$ is taken from the isotherm of the mixed film. As can be clearly observed, the Soret band intensity of the normalized spectra decreased under compression. Provided that all molecules of TSPP remain at the interface during the compression of the mixed film, the normalized reflection spectra show changes of orientation and/or association of the TSPP dye. In fact, J-aggregates are characterized by a shift of the spectral absorption band to longer wavelengths with respect to the non-aggregate state. In this mixed film, the red-shift may be due to interactions among the transition dipole moments of TSPP–TSPP or TSPP–Ir-complex neighboring molecules during the compression process. In the case of porphyrins, i.e., molecules with two components of the transition dipole μ_0 , the orientation factor is given by

$$f_{\text{orient}} = \frac{3}{4}[1 + \langle \sin^2 \theta \rangle] \quad (3)$$

with θ being the angle between the plane of the transition moments and the normal to the air–water interface (angle brackets denote average values), i.e., $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 90° for perpendicular and parallel orientation of the porphyrin ring with respect to the interface, respectively.^[43] As the Ir-complex chromophore absorbs at $\lambda_{\max} = 422$ nm (Soret band of TSPP), the contribution of the Ir-complex reflection to each spectra has to be considered and subtracted. To infer the possible change in orientation of the TSPP molecules along the compression process, a further analysis has to be done as follows.

The oscillator strength is defined as [44]

$$f = \frac{4\epsilon_0 2.303 m_e c_0}{N_A e^2} \int_{\text{band}} \epsilon d\nu = 1.44 \times 10^{-19} \int_{\text{band}} \epsilon d\nu \quad (4)$$

where ϵ_0 is the permittivity of vacuum, m_e the electron mass, e the elementary charge, c_0 the speed of light in a vacuum and N_A the Avogadro constant. In eqn (4), the numerical factor 1.44×10^{-19} is expressed in mol L⁻¹ cm s. From eqn (1) and (4) it is possible to define an apparent oscillator strength determined from the measured reflection spectra as⁴⁰

$$f_{\text{app}} = f \times f_{\text{orient}} = \frac{1.44 \times 10^{-19}}{2.303 \times 10^3 \Gamma \sqrt{R_s}} \int_{\text{band}} \Delta R d\nu \quad (5)$$

If we take into account the relationship between the surface concentration, G , in mol cm⁻², and the area per molecule, A , in nm² ($G = 10^{14}/A N_A$) and we introduce the value $R_s = 0.02$,^[41] we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} f_{\text{app}} &= f \times f_{\text{orient}} = 2.6 \times 10^{-12} \int_{\text{band}} A \Delta R d\nu \\ &= 2.6 \times 10^{-12} \int_{\text{band}} \Delta R_{\text{norm}} d\nu \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where f is the oscillator strength in solution, A is the area per molecule of TSPP, ν is the frequency, and the numeric factor 2.6×10^{-12} is expressed in $\text{nm}^{-2} \text{s}$. Thus, f_{app} can be obtained by the integration of the reflection band in the range between 385 and 450 nm, for each surface pressure. Then, from the ratio between this apparent oscillator strength, f_{app} , and the oscillator strength obtained from the solution spectrum, $f = 2.08$, the orientation factor f_{orient} can be calculated for any surface pressure (eqn (6)). At low surface pressure (0 mN m^{-1}), $f_{\text{orient}} = 1.5$ was obtained, which is the maximum value that can be obtained only if there is no loss of the porphyrin molecules into the aqueous subphase and if those molecules lie parallel to the interface, $\theta = 90^\circ$. As the Ir-complex:TSPP mixed film was compressed, the orientation factor diminished up to 1.03, together with the tilt angle, approx. 40° . This evidenced the reorientation of the porphyrin molecules under compression, changing from a flat orientation at low surface pressure to the porphyrin rings inclined by approx. 40° with respect to the normal. These considerations have been made assuming the presence of all porphyrin molecules cospread at the interface, i.e., there was no loss of molecules toward the aqueous subphase.

3 Absorption spectroscopy of Langmuir–Schaefer films

The Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) mixed monolayer was transferred at 35 mN m^{-1} from the air–water interface onto quartz substrates, by the vertical dipping Langmuir–Blodgett (LB) and horizontal touching Langmuir–Schaefer (LS) techniques. In spite of LB films being poorly transferred, the LS method led to the successful deposition of monolayers and multilayers, with transfer ratios close to 1. In these LS films, the alkyl chains of the Ir-complex in the film were directly bound to the support surface. Fig. 4 shows the UV–visible absorption spectra of different number of Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) LS layers. Both the Ir-complex and TSPP absorption bands were present, which indicated that the mixed films were successfully transferred in sequent depositions. Also, the wavelengths of the absorption peaks remained unchanged, indicating that aggregates were not formed between layers. The plot of the maximum absorption of the chromophores of each spectrum vs. the number of consecutive LS transfers revealed a linear relationship (inset in Fig. 4), indicating that the TSPP molecules, attached to the Ir-complex matrix, could be regularly deposited layer by layer.

Fig. 4 Absorption spectra of 1, 2, . . . 6 Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) LS multilayers. Inset: maximum absorption of Ir-complex ($\lambda_{\text{Ir-complex}} = 268 \text{ nm}$) and TSPP ($\lambda_{\text{TSPP}} = 427 \text{ nm}$) bands vs. number of LS layers.

Although the ratio of the transfer onto the solid support was next to unit, additional information is required to prove that the porphyrin molecules attached to the Ir-complex matrix are

correctly transferred to the substrate. For an ideal transfer process, where all Ir-complex molecules present at the air–water interface are transferred preserving their molecular orientation, the ratio between reflection and absorption is expected to be $Abs/\Delta R = 3.64$.^[34,45] The experimental ratio has been calculated at $\lambda = 268$ nm for the Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) mixed monolayer at 35 mNm⁻¹, obtaining $Abs/\Delta R = 3.45$, which was in agreement with that predicted for a complete dye transfer.^[34,45] In any case, a change of the orientation of the porphyrin molecules during the transfer process may occur.

4 Emission spectra and lifetime measurements of Langmuir–Schaefer films

Fig. 5a shows the room temperature emission spectra of the Ir-complex 1.2×10^{-5} M, TSPP 3×10^{-6} M, and the mixture Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) (same concentrations) in aerated organic solutions (dichloromethane/methanol/water, ratio 15 : 9 : 2 v/v/v), under excitation at 260 nm. As observed, the Ir-complex spectrum exhibited a broad structureless band with maximum emission at ~ 577 nm that resulted from the characteristic mixing of the ³MLCT (triplet spin-forbidden metal-to-ligand charge transfer transition) and 3LC (triplet spin-forbidden ligand centered transition) excited states of iridium complexes, ^[46] while the TSPP spectrum showed the two emission bands typical of porphyrins, Q(0,0) and Q(0,1), at 651 and 715 nm, respectively. In the case of the Ir-complex : TSPP mixture, the emission spectrum matched well with the sum of the spectra of Ir-complex and TSPP solutions. In Fig. 5b, the emission spectra of LS films of Ir-complex and Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) upon excitation at 260 nm are shown. The spectral shape of the Ir-complex LS film fitted well with that observed in solution. In contrast, the excitation of the Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) LS film led to the total quenching of the Ir-complex emission, also accompanied by a concomitant enhancement of the TSPP emission.

Fig. 5 Luminescence spectra of: (a) solutions of Ir-complex, TSPP and Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) in CH₂Cl₂/CH₃OH/H₂O (ratio 15 : 9 : 2 v/v/v), and (b) LS films of Ir-complex, Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1), Ir-complex/ DOMA : TSPP and Ir-complex/SA/DOMA : TSPP. Selected excitation wavelength = 260 nm.

The transfer efficiency E can be calculated from the luminescence intensities of the donor determined in the presence and absence of the acceptor, and is given by $E = 1 - F_{da}/F_d$, where F_d is the donor (Ir-complex) emission intensity determined at a given wavelength in the absence of the acceptor (TSPP), and F_{da} is the corresponding emission determined in the presence of the acceptor. Therefore, we obtained $E = 1$ for the Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) LS film. In fact, the energy transfer from the Ir-complex molecules to the TSPP dyes is feasible since the emission of Ir-complex occurs in the range of the Q absorption bands of the porphyrin (Fig. 4). Moreover, the distance between the Ir-complex and TSPP molecules (donor and acceptor, respectively) is short since the TSPP molecules are electrostatically attached to the Ir-complex matrix, which favors the dipole-dipole interactions among these molecules.

To study the intermolecular energy transfer, the distance between the planes of the donor and acceptor was increased by the insertion of lipid interlayers. For such a purpose, a mixed DOMA : TSPP (4 : 1) LS film was transferred onto a substrate previously covered with an Ir-complex LS film, obtaining a Ir-complex/DOMA : TSPP multilayer. The DOMA : TSPP (4 : 1) mixed monolayer has been previously investigated,²⁸ finding that both monomers and dimers of TSPP were present at high surface pressures. Furthermore, only TSPP monomers show the usual Q emission bands of porphyrins in the 625–775 nm range, while dimers have been found to exhibit Soret emission at ~ 500 nm. [47] To avoid the presence of TSPP aggregates, the mixed film has been transferred onto the Ir-complex covered substrate at 20 mN m⁻¹,

where the TSPP molecules arrange uniquely in the monomer form, and the porphyrin ring lying parallel to the surface. [28] In the fabricated film, the Ir-complex and the TSPP molecules were separated by a DOMA layer. The luminescence spectrum of this film (Fig. 5b) demonstrated that the emission of the Ir-complex was totally quenched, meaning that energy transfer to the TSPP molecules still occurred.

Finally, the donor–acceptor separation was further increased by the insertion of a fatty acid monolayer (stearic acid, SA). The film fabricated, Ir-complex/SA/DOMA : TSPP, led to the emission of the Ir-complex and the porphyrin together, indicating that the observed effective energy transfer did not take place (see Fig. 5b).

Table 1 Decay parameters, excitation wavelength and monitoring wavelength of the luminescence of Ir-complex and TSPP in different solutions and film structures.

	λ_{exc}/nm	λ_{em}/nm	τ_1/ns	τ_2/ns	χ^2
Ir-complex (solution)	372.6	575	159	—	1.159
	406.4	650	160	—	1.153
TSPP (solution)	372.6/406.4	650	9.3	—	1.125
Ir-complex/TSPP (solution)	372.6/406.4	575	166	—	1.121
	372.6	650	9.9 (38%)	182 (62%)	1.153
Ir-complex/TSPP (1 LS)	406.4	650	8.7 (81%)	126 (19%)	1.02
	406.4	575	4.7	—	1.208
Ir-complex/SA/DOMA-TSPP (1 LS)	406.4	650	4.5	—	1.231
	406.4	575	134	—	1.068
	406.4	650	5.1 (79%)	139 (21%)	1.010

The kinetic decays were performed at room temperature, monitored at 575 or 650 nm (maximum emission of Ir-complex and TSPP, respectively), under excitation at 372 and/or 406 nm. All organic solutions (dichloromethane/methanol/water, ratio 15 : 9 : 2 v/v/v) were air-equilibrated. Table 1 shows the decay parameters of the luminescence of different solutions and film structures; the excitation and the luminescence emission wavelength are also indicated.

The Ir-complex in organic solution showed a mono-exponential decay in the order of 160 ns, independent of the selected excitation and emission wavelengths. The emission of TSPP solution followed a similar behavior, with $t = 9.3$ ns. Regarding the mixture in solution, the luminescence decay monitored at 575 nm corresponded to the Ir-complex emission with $t = 166$ ns, while the decay curves measured at 650 nm have been fitted to a bi-exponential decay function, with a fast (t_1) and a slow (t_2) decay component (Table 1). From the spectroscopic data of the isolated systems at diluted conditions in solution (optical density $o0.1$), the short lifetime t_1 is regarded as the excited state lifetime of the TSPP, while the long lifetime t_2 comes from the Ir-complex luminescence. The small differences observed in lifetimes with respect to the Ir-complex in solution could be associated to some nonradiative processes such as decays due to vibrational modes and most likely also the oxygen quenching. [48]

Regarding the Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) LS film, a monoexponential fit to the decay profile was found to be highly satisfactory, independently of the detection wavelength, and no improvement of the w_2 value could be obtained when the data were fitted to a bi-exponential decay function. The calculated lifetime, $t = 4.6$ ns, clearly corresponded to the TSPP emission in the film structure. This was clear evidence of the energy transfer from the Ir-complex to the TSPP in the film. When the Ir-complex and TSPP molecules were distanced by the DOMA and SA interlayers (Ir-complex/SA/DOMA : TSPP), the emission decay curve was bi-exponential. On analyzing the decay of the emission at 650 nm, we calculated $t_1 = 5.1$ ns and $t_2 = 139$ ns, which confirmed the emission of two components of the film, i.e., TSPP and Ir-complex. The slightly shorter lifetime (139 ns) observed for the iridium metallosurfactant in the presence of SA interlayers with respect to the Ir-complex in solution (160 ns) could be mainly associated to triplet–triplet annihilation processes between molecules of Ir-complex that were

close in distance within the monolayer.[33 Additionally, the effect of oxygen on the reduction of the lifetime could not be excluded.][48]

Conclusions

In this work, the formation of a well-organized Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) monolayer at the air–water interface has been reported. In this system, the TSPP molecules were electrostatically attached underneath the amphiphilic Ir-complex matrix, forming a homogeneous monolayer from low to high surface pressures. Under compression, TSPP and Ir-complex molecules formed J-aggregates, and the porphyrin rings changed their orientation until reaching, at high surface pressure, a tilt angle $\sim 40^\circ$ with respect to the normal surface.

Similarly, Langmuir monolayers and LS films containing the pure Ir-complex have been prepared for comparison. A different number of Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) monolayers have been successfully transferred onto quartz substrates by the Langmuir–Schaefer method (LS films). The linear increase of the absorbance indicated regular deposition of the films. The energy transfer between the Ir-complex with the TSPP in solution, in a mixed film containing both dyes, and in adjacent layers of LS has been investigated. The results obtained by steady-state fluorescence and decay measurements indicated that effective intermolecular energy transfer took place in the Ir-complex : TSPP (4 : 1) LS film. In spite of the distance between donor and acceptor dyes has been increased by the insertion of a lipid monolayer, DOMA, the complete energy transfer between the Ir-complex and TSPP occurred. A longer separation, achieved by a stearic acid interlayer, led to the absence of energy transfer process.

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